

June 12-15, 2022,
Novi Sad, Serbia

EUROPE
Society for Risk Analysis

Living with Risks:

Sharing the Good Practice

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

PUBLISHER

**UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD - FACULTY OF TECHNICAL SCIENCES
21000, Novi Sad, Dositej Obradovic Square 6, Serbia**

ORGANIZER:

- **The Society for Risk Analysis – Europe (SRA-E)**
- **University of Novi Sad - Faculty of Technical Sciences,
21000, Novi Sad, Dositej Obradovic Square 6, Serbia**

EDITORS

**Mirjana Laban,
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia**
**Ljiljana Popović,
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia**

TECHNICAL EDITOR

**Ljiljana Popović,
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia**

Published in Novi Sad, June 2022
ISBN 978-86-6022-440-0

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE:

Rui Gaspar, president, Catholic University of Portugal, Portugal

Mirjana Laban, vice president, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Marja Ylönen, University of Stavanger, Norway

Frederic Boudier, University of Stavanger, Norway

Jamie Wardman, University of Nottingham, UK

Nicola Paltrinieri, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway

Anna Olofsson, Mid Sweden University, Sweden

Kalliopi Sapountzaki, Harokopio University, Greece

Angela Bearth, ETH Zurich, Switzerland

Linda Makovicka Osvaldova, University of Žilina, Slovakia

Miroslava Vandalickova, University of Žilina, Slovakia

Jasmina Gačić, University of Belgrade, Serbia

Miloš Knežević, University of Montenegro, Montenegro

Vlatko Šešov, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia

Meri Cvetkovska, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia

Elona Pojani, University of Tirana, Albania

Perseta Grabova, University of Tirana, Albania

Zvezdan Karadžin, University of Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Edisa Nukić, University of Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Gordana Broćeta, University of Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Ljiljana Popović, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Đorđe Ćosić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Srđan Popov, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Vlastimir Radonjanin, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Mirjana Malešev, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Igor Džolev, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Slobodan Kolaković, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Marko Marković, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Marija Jevtić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Ana Perišić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Tanja Vranić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Miroslav Miškić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE:

Mirjana Laban, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences (Conference chair)

Ljiljana Popović, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Đorđe Ćosić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Srđan Popov, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Tanja Vranić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Senka Bajić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Slobodan Šupić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Suzana Draganić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Marko Vuković, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Cveta Lazić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

**Sandra Nedeljković, Government of the Republic of Serbia, Public Investment
Management Office**

Sanja Mrkšić Kovačević, University of Stavanger, Norway

IT SUPPORT:

Ines Perišić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Rade Lučić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

**All of papers in this Proceedings are reviewed under control of Scientific
Committee of 30th Annual Conference of Society for Risk Analysis – Europe:
Living with Risks – Sharing the Good Practice**

SRA-E 2022

Society for Risk Analysis – Europe and Disaster Risk Management Centre, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, organize 30th Annual Conference with the general subject “Living with Risks – Sharing the Good Practice”.

The scientist and risk professionals from all areas were invited to share their knowledge and experience of applied risk analysis and science, including risk assessment, risk characterization, risk perception, risk communication, risk management, risk governance and policy, relating to risks which are of concern to individuals, organizations in the public and private sector, or to society at local, regional, national, or global levels.

This conference, as well as the previous ones, contribute from all fields dealing with risk: Environment, Disaster Risk Reduction, Fire Safety, Health and Safety at Work, Urban Safety and Security, Insurance and Finance, Project Management Risks, Cyber Security, Terrorism and all other risk topics from practice.

Members of the International Scientific Committee actively participated in the preparation of the conference, both as reviewers and authors. Annual meetings/conferences are an opportunity for risk analysts to come together to discuss issues, problems, goals and future research questions. New areas for risk analysis are emerging and new disciplines are contributing to the ongoing debate about risk analysis in its various facets.

This year the authors from 27 countries participate in the conference, and the Book of abstracts contain 116 abstracts. The editors are sincerely grateful to all the authors for the contribution to this event.

Editors

Urban and rural environment as a factor of resilience during the pandemic crisis (example from Serbia)

Slavica Dabižljević

Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Nada Tatalović

Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Marija Jevtic

Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Mirjana Laban

Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Abstract

Social and historical circumstances in the region have influenced the decline of the population's interest in the need to prepare for and respond to emergencies. Many procedures, exercises and various good practices that were previously implemented have ceased to be organized and renewed. The first reaction of the population to the pandemic was fear. This fear for the survival of the elementary cell of society - the family and its members was presented in various ways, of which uncertainty was expressed in every environment, from the lack of basic foodstuffs, as well as the lack of basic elements of modern life (regular electricity, water, heating, stable internet connection, waste disposal, disinfection of public areas, etc.).

The difference between the resilience of communities in urban and rural areas during the state of emergency in Serbia and the measures of restraint that accompanied it was the subject of research conducted immediately after this period. The research was conducted within the subject Public Health in Emergency and Crisis, at the PhD studies in the field of Disaster and Fire Risk Management, Faculty of Technical Sciences in Novi Sad. 765 respondents participated in the survey, the research methodology was adapted to the situation and is based on voluntary participation, an anonymous questionnaire and appropriate statistical processing. Respondents were asked to complete the questionnaire, according to the situation, via email, Viber or WhatsApp.

The research showed that respondents from rural areas had less uncertainty and a better quality of life during the observed period. Out of the total number of respondents, 29% of those who live in urban areas assessed that their quality of life has changed for the worse, and 18% of respondents from rural areas gave such an answer to the same question. When asked if they were worried about the possible lack of food, 29% of respondents from urban areas answered positively, and 18% of respondents from rural areas gave the same answer. Respondents living in rural areas were more satisfied with the work of utility companies.

The public health crisis caused by the COVID 19 virus represents a major test for community resilience. The research showed that rural communities showed a higher degree of resilience during the observed period. In the future, Serbia should use new experiences from the crisis and continue the good practice of training, preparation and response to emergencies at the level of local communities and organizations.

Key words: *community resilience, public health, preparation and response*